

Effectiveness of Bismuth-Based Triple Therapy Compared to Standard Triple Therapy for the Eradication of *Helicobacter pylori*

Tamilselvan T¹, Satheesh A Vasudevan², Ranjitha Balan³, Asna⁴, Josini Jose, *

¹Professor, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Nehru College of Pharmacy, Thiruvilwamala, Pampady, Thrissur, Kerala 680588 India.

²Assistant Professor, and Consultant in Gastroenterology, Centre for Gastroenterology and Hepatic Disorders, PK DAS Institute of Medical Sciences, Vaniamkulam, Ottapalam, Palakkad-679522

³Master of Pharmacy Student, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Nehru College of Pharmacy, Thiruvilwamala, Pampady, Thrissur, Kerala 680588 India.

⁴Master of Pharmacy Student, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Nehru College of Pharmacy, Thiruvilwamala, Pampady, Thrissur, Kerala 680588 India.

*Master of Pharmacy Student, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Nehru College of Pharmacy, Thiruvilwamala, Pampady, Thrissur, Kerala 680588 India.

Corresponding Author:

Ms. Josini Jose,
Master of Pharmacy Student,
Department of Pharmacy Practice,
Nehru College of Pharmacy,
Thiruvilwamala,
Pampady, Thrissur,
Kerala 680588 India.

Received: Oct 17, 2025

Accepted: Nov 13, 2025

Published: Nov 18, 2025

Abstract

Background: The infection caused by *Helicobacter pylori* continues to pose a significant global health challenge, as increasing antibiotic resistance diminishes the success rates of standard triple therapy (STT). This study aims to assess the efficacy of bismuth-based triple therapy in comparison to standard triple therapy for the eradication of *Helicobacter pylori*. **Methods:** One hundred *H. pylori*-positive adults were assigned to either STT (PPI + amoxicillin + clarithromycin) or BTT (Vonoprazan + Amoxicillin + Bismuth). Eradication was confirmed using a stool antigen test.

Results: The eradication rate was higher in the BTT group (ITT: 82%, PP: 89.1%) compared to the STT group (ITT: 68%, PP: 72.3%). The difference was statistically significant in PP analysis ($p = 0.040$). Adverse drug reactions were more frequent with STT (95.7%) than BTT (63.0%) ($p = 0.001$). Medication adherence was significantly better in BTT ($p = 0.003$).

Conclusion: Bismuth-based triple therapy has demonstrated superior eradication rates, improved adherence, and reduced side effects compared to standard triple therapy. It serves as a more effective first-line treatment, especially in areas with significant clarithromycin resistance.

Keywords: *Helicobacter pylori*, bismuth-based triple therapy, vonoprazan, eradication, antibiotic resistance.

INTRODUCTION

Helicobacter pylori is a spiral-shaped, Gram-negative bacterium that colonizes the human gastric mucosa and plays a central role in the pathogenesis of chronic gastritis, peptic ulcer disease, mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue (MALT) lymphoma, and gastric adenocarcinoma [1,2]. Since its discovery by Warren and Marshall in 1982, *H. pylori* infection has been recognized as a major public health problem worldwide, with approximately 50% of the global population infected [3]. The prevalence is notably higher in developing countries, largely due to overcrowding, poor sanitation, and limited access to healthcare [1]. The World Health Organization has classified *H. pylori* as a Class I carcinogen due to its strong association with gastric cancer [3].

Eradication of *H. pylori* infection is therefore essential for preventing gastric malignancy, promoting ulcer healing, and reducing recurrence. The conventional first-line regimen, known as standard triple therapy (STT), combines a proton pump inhibitor (PPI) with clarithromycin and amoxicillin or metronidazole for 7–14 days [4]. While initially effective, the success rate of STT has declined to below 70% in many regions, primarily because of the rise in clarithromycin and metronidazole resistance [5,6].

In contrast, bismuth-based therapies have re-emerged as an effective alternative, particularly in areas with high antibiotic resistance. Bismuth salts possess direct bactericidal properties, inhibit urease activity, and protect the gastric mucosa [6]. When combined with antibiotics and a strong acid-suppressing agent such as vonoprazan—a potassium-competitive acid blocker (P-CAB)—these regimens enhance antibiotic stability and mucosal penetration, resulting in higher eradication rates even among resistant strains [7].

Recent clinical studies and international consensus guidelines (Maastricht VI and Toronto) recommend bismuth-based therapies or non-clarithromycin regimens as the preferred first-line options in high-resistance settings [8]. However, limited data exist regarding their comparative performance in local populations. Hence, this study was undertaken to evaluate the efficacy, safety, and adherence of bismuth-based triple therapy versus standard triple therapy for *H. pylori* eradication in a tertiary care setting.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Setting: A prospective observational study was conducted at the Department of Gastroenterology, between December 2024 and October 2025, following ethical approval (IEC/14/117/25). **Study Population:** 100 adult *H. pylori*-positive patients were enrolled and divided equally into two treatment groups. Inclusion criteria included patients aged >18 years with confirmed infection; pregnant or lactating women and those with severe comorbidities were excluded. **Intervention:** Group A received standard triple therapy (proton pump inhibitor, clarithromycin, and amoxicillin), and Group B received bismuth-based triple therapy (bismuth salt, amoxicillin, and vonoprazan) for 14 days. **Assessment:** Eradication was confirmed by stool antigen test 4 weeks post-treatment. Adverse events (vomiting, diarrhea, abdominal pain, dark stools, metallic taste) and adherence (Structured Medication Adherence Scale) were assessed. **Statistical Analysis:** Data were analyzed using chi-square test; $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 100 patients meeting the inclusion criteria were enrolled, with 50 each receiving standard triple therapy (STT) or bismuth-based triple therapy (BTT). The baseline demographic characteristics, including age, sex, and comorbidities, were comparable between the groups. The mean \pm SD age was 52.7 ± 15.5 years in the STT group and 53.8 ± 16.1 years in the BTT group. Males constituted 38% in STT and 52% in BTT, showing no significant difference. Most participants presented with gastritis on endoscopy, and nearly half had no associated comorbidities.

Table 1. Baseline characteristics

Parameter	Standard Triple Therapy (STT) (n = 50)	Bismuth-Based Triple Therapy (BTT) (n = 50)
Age (years)	52.74 ± 15.46	53.76 ± 16.05
Sex (Male / Female)	19 / 31 (38 % / 62 %)	26 / 24 (52 % / 48 %)
Comorbidities present	26 (52 %)	28 (56 %)
Most common endoscopic finding	Gastritis (68 %)	Gastritis (56 %)
Pre-treatment symptoms	Abdominal pain (64 %), heartburn (22 %), others (14 %)	Abdominal pain (40 %), heartburn (34 %), others (26 %)
Alcohol consumption	11 (22 %)	8 (16 %)
Smoking	4 (8 %)	3 (6 %)
Family history of ulcer / gastritis	10 (20 %)	12 (24 %)

Eradication rates:

In the intention-to-treat (ITT) analysis, eradication of *H. pylori* was achieved in 34 (68%) of STT patients and 41 (82%) of BTT patients ($p = 0.106$). In the per-protocol (PP) analysis, 34 (72.3%) in the STT group and 41 (89.1%) in the BTT group achieved eradication, which was statistically significant ($p = 0.040$). These findings demonstrate higher efficacy for BTT compared with STT.

Adverse drug reactions:

Adverse effects were more frequent with STT, occurring in 95.7% of patients, compared with 63.0% in the BTT group ($p = 0.001$). The most common events in STT were loose stools, vomiting, and abdominal discomfort, while patients on BTT mainly reported darkened stools and a metallic taste. No serious adverse events were noted in either group.

Adherence:

Medication adherence, assessed using the Structured Medication Adherence Scale, showed that 50% of BTT patients achieved high adherence scores (9–10) compared to only 18% of those receiving STT ($p = 0.003$). Moderate adherence (scores 6–8) was observed in 60% of STT patients and 36% of BTT patients, indicating better tolerability and compliance in the bismuth-treated group.

Table 2. Comparison of treatment outcomes between STT and BTT

Outcome	Standard Triple Therapy (STT)	Bismuth-Based Triple Therapy (BTT)	p-value
Eradication rate (ITT)	34 / 50 (68.0%)	41 / 50 (82.0%)	0.106 (NS)
Eradication rate (PP)	34 / 47 (72.3%)	41 / 46 (89.1%)	0.040*
Adverse Drug Reactions (ADR)	45 / 47 (95.7%)	29 / 46 (63.0%)	0.001*
High adherence (score 9–10)	9 / 50 (18.0%)	25 / 50 (50.0%)	0.003*
Common ADRs	Vomiting, loose stools, gastric irritation	Dark stools, metallic taste	—

*NS = Not significant; *p < 0.05 = Statistically significant.

DISCUSSION

The study demonstrated that bismuth-based triple therapy achieved significantly higher eradication rates and better tolerability than standard triple therapy. The decline in STT efficacy aligns with global trends attributed to rising clarithromycin resistance [13,15]. Bismuth compounds possess direct bactericidal properties, disrupt cell walls, and inhibit urease activity, enhancing antibiotic efficacy [9]. Additionally, vonoprazan provides stronger acid suppression than proton pump inhibitors, improving antibiotic stability and bacterial eradication [7]. Comparable studies have reported eradication rates exceeding 90% with vonoprazan-based bismuth regimens, even in resistant populations [9,10]. Lower adverse effects and improved adherence observed with BTT in this study mirror international findings [15]. Given its superior performance, BTT should be preferred as a first-line therapy in high-resistance regions, in accordance with the Maastricht VI and Toronto Consensus guidelines [7,12].

CONCLUSION

Bismuth-based triple therapy demonstrated superior eradication efficacy, fewer adverse effects, and higher adherence than standard triple therapy. It represents a reliable, well-tolerated first-line regimen for *H. pylori* eradication, particularly in areas with high clarithromycin resistance. Routine surveillance of local antibiotic resistance and adherence monitoring should guide therapy selection to ensure optimal outcomes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are thankful to the Principal, Research guide, and staff of Nehru College of Pharmacy and PK DAS Institute of Medical Sciences, Vaniyamkulam for providing the necessary facilities and timely support to complete the research work.

Conflict of Interest: The authors do not have any conflicts of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Hooi JKY, Lai WY, Ng WK, Suen MMY, Underwood FE, Tanyingoh D, et al. Global prevalence of *Helicobacter pylori* infection: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Gastroenterology*. 2017;153(2):420–9.
2. International Agency for Research on Cancer. Schistosomes, liver flukes and *Helicobacter pylori*. IARC Monogr Eval Carcinog Risks Hum. 1994;61:177–241.
3. Plummer M, Franceschi S, Vignat J, Forman D, de Martel C. Global burden of gastric cancer attributable to *Helicobacter pylori*. *Int J Cancer*. 2015;136(2):487–90.
4. Malfertheiner P, Mégraud F, O'Morain CA, Gisbert JP, Kuipers EJ, Axon AT, Bazzoli F, Gasbarrini A, Atherton J, Graham DY, Hunt R. Management of *Helicobacter pylori* infection—the Maastricht V/Florence consensus report. *Gut*. 2017;66(1):6-30.
5. Graham DY, Shiotani A. New concepts of resistance in the treatment of *Helicobacter pylori* infections. *Nature clinical practice Gastroenterology & hepatology*. 2008;5(6):321-31.
6. Scarpignatoa C, Pelosinia I. Bismuth compounds for eradication of *Helicobacter pylori*: pharmacology and safety. *Clinical Pharmacology and Therapy of Helicobacter Pylori Infection*. 1999;11:85.
7. Rokkas T, Gisbert JP, Malfertheiner P, Niv Y, Gasbarrini A, Leja M, Megraud F, O'Morain C, Graham DY. Comparative effectiveness of multiple different first-line treatment regimens for *Helicobacter pylori* infection: a network meta-analysis. *Gastroenterology*. 2021;161(2):495-507.
8. Fallone CA, Moss SF, Malfertheiner P. Reconciliation of recent *Helicobacter pylori* treatment guidelines in a time of increasing resistance to antibiotics. *Gastroenterology*. 2019;157(1):44-53.

9. Tungtrongchitr N, Bongkotvirawan P, Ratana-Amornpin S, Siramolpiwat S, Eiamsitrakoon T, Gamnarai P, et al. Fourteen-day vonoprazan-based bismuth quadruple therapy for *H. pylori* eradication in an area with high clarithromycin and levofloxacin resistance: a prospective randomized study (VQ-HP trial). *Sci Rep.* 2024;14(1):8986.
10. Baig MMA, Parveen U, Farooq R, Tabassum M, Naaz F, Ibrahim Hassan S. Comparison of effectiveness of standard triple therapy versus bismuth-based therapy for the management of peptic ulcer disease due to *Helicobacter pylori*. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res.* 2020;192–5.
11. Choi SY, Lim NR, Chung WC. Tailored therapy using bismuth add-on standard triple therapy vs. Concomitant therapy: A first-line regimen for *Helicobacter pylori* infection. *Korean J Helicobacter Up Gastrointest Res.* 2023;23(2):118–24.
12. Megraud F, Bruyndonckx R, Coenen S, Wittkop L, Huang TD, Hoebeke M, Bénéjat L, Lehours P, Goossens H, Glupczynski Y. *Helicobacter pylori* resistance to antibiotics in Europe in 2018 and its relationship to antibiotic consumption in the community. *Gut.* 2021;70(10):1815-22.
13. Gisbert JP, Calvet X. non-bismuth quadruple (concomitant) therapy for eradication of *Helicobacter pylori*. *Alimentary pharmacology & therapeutics.* 2011;34(6):604-17.
14. Thung I, Aramin H, Vavinskaya V, Gupta S, Park JY, Crowe SE, Valasek MA. the global emergence of *Helicobacter pylori* antibiotic resistance. *Alimentary pharmacology & therapeutics.* 2016;43(4):514-33.
15. Liou JM, Fang YJ, Chen CC, Bair MJ, Chang CY, Lee YC, Chen MJ, Chen CC, Tseng CH, Hsu YC, Lee JY. Concomitant, bismuth quadruple, and 14-day triple therapy in the first-line treatment of *Helicobacter pylori*: a multicentre, open-label, randomised trial. *The Lancet.* 2016;388(10058):2355-65.

